

Bioaccumulation of lead (Pb), chromium (Cr) and cadmium (Cd) by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Fusarium oxysporum* isolated from tannery wastewater

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ABSTRACT

Fifty (50) fungal isolates were isolated from tannery wastewater from our previous experiment of which *Aspergillus flavus* and *Fusarium oxysporum* were the most dominant and least fungal species identified. The concentration of the three heavy metals in the tannery wastewater and mycelia of the two fungal isolates were determined before and after the remediation studies. This was done by digesting 1.0g of the fungal mycelia tissue of each of the isolates using 17.5 ml of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and 12.5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl). This was followed by subsequent heating to dryness and making up the volume of the digest to 50 ml using sterile distilled water. The digest was then filtered to remove insoluble material that could clog the atomizer and the filtrates were then analyzed for Pb, Cr and Cd using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The growths of the tested fungi were monitored in Potato dextrose broth (PDB) medium amended with untreated tannery wastewater in the ratio 1:3 for a period of one week (7 days). The heavy metal uptake and removal capacity of the test fungi was calculated according to standard procedures. With respect to Pb, Cr and Cd, maximum uptake of 42.00, 88.00 and 29.00 mg/g was observed for *F. oxysporum*, while 36.00, 23.46 and 1.09 mg/g was observed for *A. flavus* respectively. Both fungal isolates were further characterized using molecular approach to confirm their identity. Therefore, it was concluded that these identified fungi have the potential as bio-sorbent for the remediation of sites contaminated with Pb, Cr and Cd respectively.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Heavy metals constitute a major pollutant group seldom found in tannery effluents and the tannery wastewater in particular, is a potential environmental issue especially when disposed unsafely [1,2,3,]. Often, the level of both organic and inorganic pollutants in the tannery wastes far exceeds those deemed to be environmentally safe [2]. In a related study, chromium was found to be closely associated with soil contaminated with tannery sludge in the vicinity of some functional tanneries within Sokoto metropolis [4]. Therefore, it is conceivable that the continuous release of wastewater from tanneries into the environment could lead to heavy metal pollution of the recipient sites which ultimately leaches to ground water [5]. Unsafe disposal of tannery wastewater causes serious health hazards such

as liver damage, pulmonary congestion and Oedema [6] due to the presence of toxic heavy metals [7].

A recurring challenge to the problem of heavy metal pollution is the lack of affordable, efficient and reliable methods of heavy metal reduction or total removal. In most instances, some are overshadowed with many problems [8,9].

Over the years, the use of microorganisms as an alternative to traditional methods such as precipitation, oxidation or reduction, filtration and ion exchange, in current use, has seen the green light due to better performance, availability and affordability. Currently, bacteria [10,11] and Fungi [12,13,14] have been utilized. Past studies have shown that the use of microorganisms as heavy metals remediating agents hold promise as eco-friendly alternative

approaches and could definitely meet the challenges surrounding heavy metal pollution [15]. Members of the *Aspergillus* species have been isolated from tannery wastewater polluted sites and their resistance to high concentrations of toxic metals has been tested [16]. Their capacity to bioaccumulate heavy metals is distinguishable among the fungal community [17]. In our study, we were able to show that the fungal isolates simultaneously bioaccumulate and removed three different toxic heavy metals and no significant difference was recorded with regards to heavy metals bioremoval from the tannery wastewater.

This research investigates the potential of *Aspergillus Flavus* and *Fusarium oxysporum* to bioaccumulate heavy metals (Pb, Cr and Cd) in wastewater from tanneries within Sokoto metropolis.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Sample collection

Wastewater samples were collected from untreated wastewater reservoir of Tudun-Wada, Unguwar Rogo I and Unguwar Rogo II tanneries in Sokoto metropolis for the mycoremediation studies. The samples were collected in duplicate by lowering the plastic containers 30 cm deep into the mixed section of sampling point. At each sampling point, 500 ml of the sample were collected in new plastic containers. Another 200 ml of the sample was collected into sterile sampling bottles at each sampling point for the analysis of Pb, Cr and Cd content in the wastewater. All samples were stored in an ice-cold box and transported to the laboratory for analysis [17].

2.2 Fungal isolates

The fungal isolates tested for their capacity to bioaccumulate Pb, Cr and Cd from the tannery wastewater were obtained from a previous work on heavy metal resistance potential of some *Aspergillus* species isolated from tannery wastewater [18]. Both isolates have been tested and found to be tolerant to 5, 10 and 15 µg/ml of Pb, Cr and Cd [18]. The two fungal isolates were reactivated by subculturing into freshly prepared potato dextrose agar (PDA) to confirm their viability and purity.

2.3 Determination of Pb, Cr and Cd in the test fungal isolates

The isolates having been isolated from tannery wastewater must have accumulated certain amount of Pb, Cr and Cd in their mycelia tissues during their period of stay in the wastewater and also in wastewater contaminated sites. Therefore, the levels of heavy metals in the mycelia of the test isolates were determined prior to the mycoremediation studies. This was done by digesting 1.0g of the fungal mycelia tissue of each of the isolates using 17.5 ml of

concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and 12.5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl). This was followed by subsequent heating to dryness and making up the volume of the digest to 50 ml using sterile distilled water. The digest was then filtered to remove insoluble material that could clog the atomizer and the filtrates were then analyzed for Pb, Cr and Cd using atomic absorption spectrophotometer AA6800 [17].

2.4 Determination of Pb, Cr and Cd in the tannery wastewater

The heavy metals content of the tannery wastewater was determined by digesting duplicate 5 ml of the wastewater using 17.5 ml of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and 12.5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl). This was followed by subsequent heating of the mixture to dryness and making up the volume of the digest to 50 ml using distilled water. The filtrate was then analyzed for Pb, Cr and Cd using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) AA6800 [17].

2.5 Determination of heavy metal uptake and bioaccumulation by the test fungal isolates

This was determined according to methods of Ezeonuegbu *et al.* [21]. Each of the test fungal isolates was inoculated into duplicate 250 ml conical flasks containing sterilized potato dextrose broth (PDB) mixed with autoclaved raw tannery wastewater in the ratio 3:1. Similarly, the isolates were inoculated into duplicate conical flasks containing only PDB to serve as control. This was followed by incubating the inoculated flasks aerobically at 35°C for 7 days. All the cultures were aseptically filtered through a pre-weighed Whatman filter paper (No. 1) to separate the mycelial mat from the spent cultures. The harvested mycelial mats were oven dried at 70°C for 18 hours. The weight of the dried mycelial mats was measured using an electronic weighing balance. The difference between the weight of the filter paper bearing the mycelial mat and the weight of the filter paper represent the fungal biomass expressed as dry weight in mg/flask. The metal uptake capacity of the test fungal isolates was calculated using the formula below in accordance with Javaid and Bajwa [19] and Burgess and Almeid [20] and Joshi *et al.* [13].

$$Q = \frac{V(C_f - C_i)}{W} \times 1000$$

Where Q= amount of metal taken up and accumulated by the fungal biomass (mg/g)

C_i= concentration of metal ions on the fungi before accumulation

C_f = concentration of metal ion on the fungi after accumulation

V= total working volume

W= dry weight of the fungal biomass.

The filtrate of the experimental cultures was analyzed for the presence of residual Pb, Cr and Cd in the wastewater using Atomic Absorption

Spectrophotometer (AA6800). The heavy metals removal was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Metal removal} = \frac{(X-Y) \times 100\%}{X}$$

Where, X and Y are the initial and final concentrations of metal ions in the filtrate (Wastewater) before and after inoculation of the test fungi respectively.

2.6 DNA extraction and purification

The fungal isolates were grown on PDA medium. The plates were incubated at 30 °C for 5 days. The fungal mycelia were used for DNA extraction according to methods of [21].

Mycelium of the fungal culture was scraped from the surface of the culture media using a sterilized needle. Approximately 0.1g of the mycelia tissue from the culture fungi was transferred to a 1.5µl tube of which 400µl of lysis buffer and 10µl proteinase K have been added. The tube was placed on a heat block at 60°C for 1hour. Subsequently, 400µl of phenol/chloroform (1:1) was added to the lysate and vortexed briefly, spin at 1000rpm for 10minutes to separate the phases. The upper layer was carefully transferred into a 1.5µl tube without extracting the white interface. Equal volumes of 100% ethanol and 3M sodium acetate were added into the tube and mixed by inverting the tube several times before incubating at -20°C overnight. After incubation, the tube was spin at 1400rpm for 10mins in a refrigerated centrifuge. The ethanol was pipette followed by the addition of 400µl of 70% ethanol and spinning at 1400rpm at 4°C. The ethanol was completely removed and the tube was spin at high speed for 30sec to ensure no traces of ethanol was left. The DNA was dried leaving the tubes open for 10mins. The pelleted DNA was suspended into 50µl of sterile distilled water and stored at -20°C prior to subsequent analysis. DNA concentration and A260/A280 ratio were determined with a biophotometer (Biophotometer plus Eppendorf Germany). An A260/A280 ratio of 1.8-2.1 was considered acceptable for PCR.

2.6.1 Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

For identification of the fungal isolates, DNA of each isolate was amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using two different Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) primers sets (ITS 1: TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG and ITS 4: TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC) [22]. A 20µl PCR reaction mixture was prepared, which contained 16µl of H₂O, 1µl primer 1 and 2 and 2µl template (DNA extract). The PCR amplifications were conducted using a thermal cycler (PTC 100). The PCR cycles included initial denaturing for 3mins at 95°C; 35cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 40sec, annealing at 54°C for 45s and extension at 72°C for 1min; followed by final extension at 72°C for 10min along with negative and positive controls. The negative control consisting of a reaction mixture

without template DNA was included in every PCR reaction together with positive control consisting of a reaction mixture containing a template of a known organism. The DNA samples were subjected to amplification by direct amplification of the ITS1 and 4 primers. A sample (5µl) of the PCR products were electrophoresed in 1% agarose gel in 1x Tris-acetate EDTA (TAE) buffer stained with ethidium bromide to determine its quantity and integrity.

2.6.2 DNA sequencing

The purified amplicons were sequenced by using an automated sequencer (Bioneer, Korea). Sequences were compared against known sequences in the NCBI database for species identification using the Blast program (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast>) [23].

2.7 Statistical analysis

All experiments were performed with three replicates. The metal uptake and removal by the two isolates were subjected to analysis of variance using graph pad (PRISM software) at p<.05.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Heavy metal uptake from wastewater of the tanneries by the test fungal isolates

The result shows that *Fusarium oxysporum* had the highest uptake for Pb (60.0mg/g), while *Aspergillus flavus* had an uptake of (55.0mg/g) Fig.1. The highest Cr uptake was recorded by *F. oxysporum* (88.0mg/g) while *A. flavus* had an uptake of (23.46mg/g). *F. oxysporum* also recorded the highest Cd uptake (29.0mg/g) and *A. flavus* had an uptake of (1.09mg/g). The heavy metal bioaccumulation by the test fungal isolates observed in this study agrees with reports from previous studies [16,12] and there was no significant difference (p<.05) in amount of metals bioaccumulated by the test isolates. The results revealed that high bioaccumulation for Pb, Cr and Cd were observed for *F. oxysporum*.

The accumulation of metal ions from solution by fungi involves several mechanisms that have been proposed [24,13,25,14]. Results obtained from this study, strongly suggests bioaccumulation to be the dominant mechanism. This assertion lends support from the reports of Volesky [26] and Ledin *et al.* [27], which stated that, fungi belonging to the genera *Aspergillus sp.*, *Penicillium sp.* and *Fusarium sp.* have high capacity for bioaccumulation of heavy metals. Accumulation of metals is carried out by initial binding of metal ions onto the negatively charged cell wall followed by penetration into their cytoplasm and gets accumulated inside the cell [28,29]. This was as well reported by Salman *et al.* [30] who reported that the metal binding capacity of fungi depends on the

presence of functional amine, phosphate, sulphate, sulfhydryl, carboxyl and hydroxyl groups on the cell wall materials like chitin and chitosan which are able to bind metal ions to a greater or lesser extent.

In this study, the fungal isolates accumulated a substantial high amount of Pb, Cr and Cd probably due to the presence of cysteine rich metallothienes. This protein shows higher affinity towards these metals [31].

Figure 1. Uptake of Pb, Cr and Cd by the test fungal isolates isolated from tannery wastewater.

3.2 Percentage removal of heavy metals from the wastewater by the resistant fungal isolates

The fungal isolates were further tested for their ability to remove the heavy metals from the wastewater. Fig. 2 shows the results of the percentage removal of Pb, Cr and Cd from the wastewater by the resistant fungal isolates. The results shows that both isolates showed the potential (67.44- 76.7%) to remove Pb from the wastewater.

With regards to Cr, *A. flavus* had the capacity to remove higher amount of Cr (36%) from the wastewater, while *F. oxysporum* removed only (33%). It was also observed that both isolates vary greatly in their capacity to remove Cd from the wastewater of the tanneries. *A. flavus* was able to remove higher percentage of Cd (81.25%) while *F. oxysporum* was able to remove only 48.51% of Cd. The fungal isolates exhibited the ability to remove all the metal ions simultaneously which was species dependent and different from metal to metal. This observation agrees with earlier report made by Burgess and Almeida [20]. The observation in heavy metal removal made in this study was similar to findings reported by Kapoor *et al.* [32] and Dias *et al.* [33] who observed that *A. flavus*, *A. oryzae*, *A. niger* have high capacity for the removal of metal ions from aqueous solutions. Similar findings of Tapan *et al.* [34] also reported that ionic groups of cell wall surface such as glucuronic acids, phosphates and cis-

oriented hydroxyl groups act as ligands in intracellular sequestration of metals which result in the removal of the metals from aqueous culture medium. Such activities in the case of fungi have been reported in literature during metal bioremoval [35,36]. The removal of Pb, Cr and Cd by *A. flavus* strongly suggests that this fungal species could be relied upon in the remediation of heavy metal polluted wastes. The performance of both isolates observed in this study further supports the view that filamentous fungi offer great hope in our efforts to circumvent the problem of heavy metal pollution of both aquatic and terrestrial environments.

3.3 Identification of the metal resistant fungal isolates

The identity of the strains was confirmed using 18S rDNA sequence analysis following comparison with sequences in the NCBI (Table 1). The two isolates were identified as *Aspergillus flavus* and *Fusarium oxysporum* which confirms with our earlier identification based on macroscopic and microscopic observations. Ezzouhri *et al.* [31] isolated fungi belonging to the genera *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Alternaria* and *Geotrichum* from heavy metal contaminated sites in Tangier, Morocco. The presence of microorganisms in heavy metals polluted niche suggests that such organisms must have adapted and developed mechanism of resistance to these toxic heavy metals.

Figure 2. Removal of Pb, Cr and Cd by the test fungal isolates isolated from tannery wastewater.

Table 1. Alignment of partial 18S rDNA sequences of fungal isolates isolated from tannery wastewater.

Isolates	Identity (%)	Species (Accession Number)
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	99	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (KX067886.1)
	98	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (FJ654480.1)
	99	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (KX067852.1)
	99	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (KP721599.1)
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	99	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> (KU097320.1)
	99	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> (KC963036.1)
	99	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> (KF534747.1)
	99	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> (JN400690.1)

4. CONCLUSION

The fungal isolates varied greatly in their capacity to bio-accumulate the test heavy metals in their tissue. The highest heavy metals uptake by the test fungal isolates was recorded by *F. oxysporum*. The fungal isolates also showed variation in the removal of Pb, Cr and Cd from the wastewater samples. The present study has revealed that the fungal isolates have the capacity to remove or bioaccumulate Pb, Cr

and Cd from tannery wastewater. Hence, these filamentous fungi can be utilized in the mycoremediation of sites polluted with such metals.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

MA designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. ADI managed the analyses of the study and assisted in the analyses of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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